

STRENGTH TRAINING'S IMPACT ON LIGA NG MGA AGILANG MANANAYAW DANCERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 8

Pages: 886-890

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3013

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14827996

Manuscript Accepted: 01-18-2025

Strength Training's Impact on Liga ng mga Agilang Mananayaw Dancers

Glezyl P. Julieto,* Bryan L. Cancio

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Strength training is a critical component of dancers' physical preparation, aimed at enhancing muscular strength and bone health while minimizing pain and reducing the risk of serious injuries. This study employed a quantitative descriptive-comparative research design to investigate the level of strength training among 35 BPE-SPE student dancers from the Liga ng mga Agilang Mananayaw, selected through simple random sampling. The research was grounded in Thorndike's Learning Theory, which posits that behaviors followed by positive consequences are more likely to be repeated, while those followed by negative consequences are less likely to recur. The study utilized the theory's principles—law of effect, law of exercise, and law of readiness—to frame the analysis of strength training practices and their impact on dancers' performance. Data collection was conducted using an adapted survey questionnaire, and statistical analyses, including mean t-tests and ANOVA, were performed. Results indicated that the student dancers exhibited high levels of strength training in terms of core strength, lower body strength, and upper body strength, signifying consistent engagement in strength training exercises. Moreover, no significant differences were observed in the levels of strength training across variables such as age, year level, and sex. Based on the findings, it is recommended that the school administration, sports coordinator, and dance club moderator collaborate to provide additional support for the dance club, such as strength training equipment, to sustain and enhance the athletic performance of student dancers.

Keywords: *strength training, dancers, Thorndike's Learning Theory, injury prevention, athletic performance*

Introduction

Strength training is a form of exercise that involves muscle contractions against external resistance, designed to enhance muscle mass, strengthen bones, improve balance, and promote overall quality of life by increasing physical capacity (Penn State College of Medicine Research, 2021). For dancers, strength training provides an opportunity to deepen their understanding of their bodies, emphasizing athleticism during performances and reducing the risk of injuries (Harrison, 2024). Despite their light and graceful appearance, dancers are particularly prone to injuries due to the overuse of joints and muscles, particularly in the ankles, legs, feet, and lower back, often resulting in stress fractures. As such, dancers require exceptional levels of flexibility, stamina, and strength to meet the demands of their art (Lasner & Greene, 2021).

Research conducted at Cleveland State University in Ohio highlights the heightened risk of musculoskeletal injuries among professional and pre-professional ballet dancers. Repetitive execution of complex movements at extreme ranges of joint motion often affects areas such as the foot, ankle, lumbosacral spine, knee, and hip. These injuries not only pose risks for chronic musculoskeletal conditions but can also lead to premature retirement, high medical costs, and significant implications for the dance community (Long et al., 2021).

In the Western Visayas region of the Philippines, a study on competitive dance-sport athletes in modern standard and Latin-American dances revealed that common injuries include herniated cervical discs, stiff necks, posterior tibial tendonitis, and hamstring strains. Latin-American dancers are particularly prone to shoulder injuries due to the greater difficulty level of their routines. The findings underscore the importance of warm-up exercises before training and competitions to maintain muscle strength and reduce the risk of injury caused by the physical demands of dance activities (Portugalete et al., 2023).

Similarly, research conducted at the Davao del Norte Regional Sports Academy during the pandemic revealed that student-athletes faced challenges in maintaining their physical health. Self-training and home exercises were less effective than face-to-face training, leaving athletes feeling physically weak and more susceptible to injuries. These findings highlight the necessity of structured strength training programs tailored to athletes' specific needs to prevent injuries and enhance performance (Indie, 2022).

Despite the growing body of literature on strength training and its benefits, there remains a significant gap in understanding how student dancers perceive and participate in strength training programs. The present study focuses on the student dancers of the Liga ng mga Agilang Mananayaw in a private institution in Davao City. This research seeks to address the urgent need to explore the role of strength training in enhancing dancers' performance and preventing injuries, thereby contributing valuable insights into the development of effective training programs for dancers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to describe the level of strength training among student dancers. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of:

- 1.1. age;
- 1.2. year level; and
- 1.3. sex?
2. What is the level of strength training for dancers in terms of:
 - 2.1. core strength;
 - 2.2. lower body strength; and
 - 2.3. upper body strength?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of strength training for dancers when analyzed across the profile of the respondents?

Methodology

The study utilized a quantitative research design with a descriptive-comparative approach. Quantitative research methods systematically collect and analyze numerical data to observe patterns, establish relationships, and draw conclusions about a specific population (Sreekumar, 2024). Specifically, the descriptive-comparative approach, also referred to as causal-comparative or "ex post facto," examines pre-existing differences in groups to identify potential causes or effects that have already occurred (Rose, 2017).

This methodology allowed the researchers to assess the level of strength training among student dancers and compare differences based on demographic variables, such as age, year level, and sex.

This study was conducted at School B, a private non-sectarian academic institution located in Davao City, Philippines, offering Senior High School and Baccalaureate Degree Programs. The respondents were 35 Bachelor of Physical Education and Sports and Physical Education (BPE-SPE) student-dancers, all active members of the Liga ng mga Agilang Mananayaw (LIAM) dance club during the second semester of the academic year 2023–2024. These student dancers represented the College of Human Kinetics in various events, including production numbers, school intramurals, dance extravaganzas, and competitions under the BPEd XI Leagues. Their participation in this study provided valuable insights into their strength training practices and performance enhancement.

Data were collected using an adapted survey questionnaire based on the instrument developed by Shurley et al. (2020) in their study, "Strength and Conditioning Practices of Head Coaches of Male and Female Interscholastic Sport Teams." The questionnaire comprised two sections.

The first section captured the demographic profile of the respondents, while the second assessed their strength training levels. The latter consisted of 15 items divided into three subcategories: core strength, lower body strength, and upper body strength. Each subcategory contained five items rated on a 5-point Likert scale, where 5 indicated "strongly agree" and 1 indicated "strongly disagree."

Statistical analysis was employed to interpret the data effectively. Measures of central tendency, particularly the mean, were used to describe the overall level of strength training among student dancers. An independent samples t-test was conducted to determine whether there were significant differences in strength training levels based on sex.

Additionally, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to examine differences in strength training levels when respondents were grouped according to age and year level. These analyses provided a comprehensive understanding of the variations in strength training practices among the respondents.

This methodology was designed to provide a systematic and reliable assessment of the strength training practices of the student dancers. The findings aim to contribute to the development of tailored strength training programs that enhance dancers' physical performance, reduce the risk of injuries, and support their overall athletic development. By addressing gaps in knowledge regarding strength training in dance, this study seeks to benefit both practitioners and educators in the field of dance and sports education.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis of the collected data, interpretations and statistical techniques that are utilized in the current study.

Profile of the Respondents

This section presents the respondents' profiles in terms of age, sex, and year level. Table 1 presents the respondent's profile, frequency, and percentage.

In terms of age, the result shows that 20 to 21 years old obtained the highest percentage of 62.86, while the lowest percentage is garnered by 24 to 25 years old with 8.57. It means that more than half of the respondents are around 20 to 21 years old.

The next profile variable is sex. It is categorized as male and female. The result shows that 65.71 percent of the respondents are female, and 34.29 percent are male. It means that a higher number of the respondents surveyed are female.

The last profile variable is the year level of the respondents. The result shows that the respondents from the third-year level obtained the highest percentage of 91.43%, while the lowest percentage is garnered from the second-year level with 2.86. Furthermore, the respondents tally a total of 35.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

Profile	Frequency	Percent
1.1 Age		
18-19 years old	0	0%
20-21 years old	22	62.86%
22-23 years old	10	28.57%
24-25 years old	3	8.57%
Total	35	100%
1.2 Sex		
Male	12	34.29%
Female	23	65.71%
Total	35	100%
1.3 Year Level		
First Year	2	5.71%
Second Year	1	2.86%
Third Year	32	91.43%
Fourth Year	0	0%
Total	35	100%

Level of Strength Training among Student-Dancers of the Liga ng mga Agilang Mananayaw

The table below provides an overview of the strength training among student dancers assessing various dimensions, including core strength, lower body strength, and upper body strength. Table 2 shows the summary of the level of strength training among student dancers, garnering an overall mean score of 3.59. This numerical statistical result indicates a high descriptive level, which denotes that strength training among student-dancers is often evident within the school setting. It implies that they have the same level of strength in different types of training. This is supported by Kipouridis (2023), who said that strength training has been shown to assist in elevation, balance, the ability to handle complex, virtuosic repertoire, the control of movement, and enhance a dancer’s overall individual style. Improving strength also helps a dancer become a more versatile performer as well as being able to meet their physical dance needs with ease and is correlated with a lower risk of injury.

Table 2. *Summary of the Level of Strength Training among Student-Dancers of the Liga ng mga Agilang Mananayaw*

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Core Strength	3.52	High
Lower Body Strength	3.70	High
Upper Body Strength	3.53	High
Overall Mean	3.59	High

The table revealed that the level of core strength of student-dancers obtained an overall mean score of 3.52. This numerical statistical result indicates a high descriptive level, which denotes that strength training among student-dancers is often evident. This showed that the respondents were doing front squats to strengthen the core muscles. The core strength plays a role in coordinating the force of the entire body. Core strength is the foundation of body stability. It is an essential physical quality in sports dance programs (Yue, 2023).

Next, the level of lower body strength of student dancers obtained an overall mean score of 3.70. This numerical statistical result indicates a high descriptive level, which denotes that strength training among student-dancers is often evident. This implies that the respondents were doing power-clean exercises to build muscles in their lower body. This result strengthens the idea of Cronkleton (2020), which states that a strong lower body helps to improve overall athletic performance because leg workouts engage the major muscle groups of your body. Moreover, this will also help to prevent injury and manage chronic conditions such as arthritis, heart disease, and diabetes.

Lastly, the level of upper body strength training among student dancers obtained an overall mean score of 3.53. This numerical statistical result indicates a high descriptive level, which denotes that strength training among student-dancers is often evident. This implies that the respondents were doing body weight training to have a stronger upper body. Ferguson and Stevenson (2017) explained that upper body strength can help dancers have higher jumps, better turns, and stronger balances. Having a stronger torso assists the dancers in executing dance movements with precision, which avoids chronic injury by evenly displacing force within muscles.

Test of Difference in the Level of Strength Training for Student-Dancers When Analyzed Across the Profile of the Respondents

The table below presents the test of difference in the level of strength training for dancers when analyzed across the profile of the respondents.

In terms of age, it garners an F-value of .167 with a p-value of .847 which is greater than 0.5 in the level of significance, indicating that there is no significant difference. The null hypothesis cannot be rejected, indicating that the level of strength training does not vary significantly across different age groups.

Table 3. *Test of Difference in the Level of Strength Training for Student-Dancers When Analyzed Across the Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>F/t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision on Ho</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Age	.167	.847	Failed to Reject	Not significant
Sex	3.518	.070	Failed to Reject	Not significant
Year Level	.651	.528	Failed to Reject	Not significant

In terms of gender, it shows a t-value of 3.518 with a p-value of .070 which is greater than 0.5 in the level of significance, indicating that there is no significant difference. The null hypothesis fails to be rejected. Moreover, this implies that the level of strength training is similar between male and female student-dancers.

In addition, in terms of year level, it records an F-value of .651 with a p-value of .528 which is greater than 0.5 in the level of significance, indicating that there is no significant difference. The null hypothesis cannot be rejected, indicating that the level of strength training does not vary significantly among different year levels of college student-dancers from first year to fourth year.

These findings indicate that the factors of age, gender, and year level do not have a significant impact on the level of strength training among student-dancers. It suggests that the student dancers' strength training is consistent across these demographic factors.

Conclusions

The analysis of data revealed a high level of strength training among student dancers, specifically in terms of core strength, lower body strength, and upper body strength. Statistical tests, including the independent samples t-test and analysis of variance (ANOVA), were employed to examine differences in strength training levels across demographic variables such as age, year level, and sex. The findings indicated that there were no statistically significant differences among the groups, suggesting that strength training levels were consistent regardless of these demographic factors. Consequently, the null hypothesis could not be rejected.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that the strength training program for student-dancers be sustained and further enhanced. Such programs not only improve athletic performance but also contribute to better body mechanics, posture, and injury prevention before, during, and after dance activities. These benefits underline the importance of maintaining regular and structured strength training as part of the dancers' routine.

To further support the initiative, the school administration, sports coordinator, and the moderator of Liga ng mga Agilang Mananayaw (LIAM) should collaborate to provide additional resources, such as specialized strength training equipment. This investment would help student dancers sustain and improve their performance levels while fostering greater participation and motivation in training and dance activities.

Moreover, encouraging student dancers to engage in strength training actively can inspire them to excel in the dance field, build resilience, and share their skills with new members of the dance club. Such efforts will not only elevate the performance standards of LIAM but also ensure the continuity and growth of its legacy in future generations.

In conclusion, this study highlights the critical role of strength training in enhancing the physical and performance capabilities of student dancers. By addressing the identified needs and implementing the recommended strategies, stakeholders can ensure a supportive and sustainable environment that promotes excellence in dance education and performance.

References

- Cronkleton, E. (2020). Why do people say to never skip a leg day? Healthline. <https://www.healthline.com/health/exercise-fitness/never-skip-leg-day#benefits-of-leg-days>
- Ferguson, H., & Stevenson, R. (2017). Upper body strength in dancers. Magnathrapy-2. <https://www.magnapt.com/post/2017/09/01/upper-body-strength-in-dancers>
- Harrison, J. (2024). Strength training for dancers shouldn't look like dance — Present Tense Fitness. Present Tense Fitness. <https://www.presenttensefitness.com/dance-and-sports-performance/2024/2/14/strength-training-for-dancers-shouldnt-look-like-dance>
- Indie, E. (2022). Physical and mental health challenges of student-athletes in the midst of the pandemic: A lockdown chronicles. International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology. <https://ijisrt.com/assets/upload/files/IJISRT22JUL309.pdf>
- Kipouridis, S. (2023). Importance of strength training for dancers. Performance Medicine. <https://performancemedicine.com.au/strength-for-dancers/>
- Lasner, A., & Greene, A. (2021). Common dance injuries and prevention tips. Johns Hopkins Medicine. <https://www.hopkinsmedicine.org/health/conditions-and-diseases/sports-injuries/common-dance-injuries-and-prevention-tips>
- Long, K. L., Milidonis, M. K., Wildermuth, V. L., Kruse, A. N., & Parham, U. T. (2021). The impact of dance-specific neuromuscular

conditioning and injury prevention training on motor control, stability, balance, function, and injury in professional ballet dancers: A mixed-methods quasi-experimental study. *International Journal of Sports Physical Therapy*, 16(2), 404–417. <https://doi.org/10.26603/001c.21150>

Penn State College of Medicine Research. (2021, August 11). Introduction to strength training. Penn State College of Medicine Research. <https://research.med.psu.edu/oncology-nutrition-exercise/patient-guides/strength-training/>

Portugalete, T. E. (2023). Injuries and injury management among DanceSport competitors in Western Visayas, Philippines. *Dbpia*. <https://doi.org/10.26584/RDPA.2023.12.7.3.1>

Rose, L. (2017, July 19). Causal comparative research design. SlidePlayer. <https://slideplayer.com/slide/10747531/>

Shurley, J. P., Ednie, A. J., & Rudebeck, T. J. (2020). Strength and conditioning practices of head coaches of male and female interscholastic sport teams. *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*, 34(7), 1894–1902. <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000003624>

Simply Psychology. (2024, February 1). Edward Thorndike: The law of effect. Simply Psychology. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/edward-thorndike.html>

Sreekumar, D. (2024, January 8). What is quantitative research? Definition, methods, types, and examples. *Researcher.Life*. <https://researcher.life/blog/article/what-is-quantitative-research-types-and-examples/>

Yue, H. (2023). Core strength training impacts on the improvement of muscle coordination in sport dancers. *Revista Brasileira de Medicina do Esporte*, 29. https://doi.org/10.1590/1517-8692202329012022_0292

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Glezyl P. Julieto

St. John Paul II College of Davao – Philippines

Bryan L. Cancio

Holy Cross of Davao College – Philippines